
PEDAGOGY AND TEACHER PROFESSIONALISM

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Annotation: This article covers significant information about importance of pedagogy and teacher professionalism in our society. On the other hand, basic clusters of pedagogical approaches were noted.

Key words: *Pedagogical accomplishment, complex interaction, supportive climate, cognitive activation, pedagogical knowledge, professionalism, teacher learning, theoretical models.*

Education is a fundamental aspect in the development of a country. If the youth of a society is educated, a future is born. Teachers provide the education that improves quality of life, therefore bringing so much to both individuals and society as a whole. Teachers are arguably the most important members of our society. They give children purpose, set them up for success as citizens of our world, and inspire in them a drive to do well and succeed in life. The children of today are the leaders of tomorrow, and teachers are that critical point that makes a child ready for their future. Teachers have the ability to shape leaders of the future in the best way for society to build positive and inspired future generations and therefore design society, both on a local and global scale. In reality, teachers have the most important job in the world. Those who have an impact on the children of society have the power to change lives. Not just for those children themselves, but for the lives of all. Teachers can act as a support system that is lacking elsewhere in students' lives. They can be a role model and an inspiration to go further and to dream bigger. They hold students accountable for their successes and failures and

good teachers won't let their talented students get away with not living up to their full potential[1]. Teachers of all walks of life and subjects have the ability to shape opinions and help form ideas about society, life and personal goals. Teachers can also expand students' limits and push their creativity.

Pedagogical accomplishment and expertise are at the core of teacher professionalism. A strong focus on pedagogy is needed in order to understand and promote teacher professional competences. However, pedagogy also presents formidable analytical problems to grasp given the sheer number and the dynamism of the relationships involved; there are no widely agreed definitions; and because pedagogy encapsulates a complex interaction of knowledge and practice. Teaching is an art as well as a science. Even teachers often find it difficult to talk about their teaching, compared with discussing the curriculum, learning, or classroom management. Professional expertise is both about the practical complex art of teaching and the design of learning environments to get the most from the teaching and pedagogy[2]. Pedagogical expertise is exercised through good classroom management, ensuring a supportive climate, and assessment. "Classroom management" is how teachers keep students organized, attentive and focused; "supportive climate" refers to the student teacher relationship and is high when teachers give positive and constructive feedback; "cognitive activation" means teaching that fosters student cognitive engagement with the subject matter. Expert teachers consistently achieve these tasks. Different pedagogies have developed different ways of balancing these three tasks, and to achieve these three components, expert teachers draw on a combination of pedagogical approaches.

Pedagogy also needs to be combined with expertise in the design of learning environments to get the most out of it. To understand the teaching profession as one in which professionals are steeped in teaching and learning requires the focus on pedagogy, where they connect scientific theories to their daily experiences and particular contexts. The view of teachers is evolving from technicians who implement the educational ideas and procedures of the curriculum to teachers as

designers of learning environments and as experts in the art and science of teaching. Making the core pedagogical knowledge that defines teacher professionalism more visible should enhance teachers' status rather than diminish it. Teacher professionalism depends on collaborative learning, design and networking and is not reducible to a set of individual traits. Concepts of professionalism are often highly individualistic and assumed to reside in the knowledge and capabilities of individual teachers. In fact, this report shows that professionalism depends on collaborative learning and design, and active networking. It is precisely through the idea of teachers as designers of learning that innovation at the level of practice can be seen as a normal side of the teaching profession to solve the daily challenges in a context which is in constant change. Bringing pedagogy to the fore is to recognize the professional expertise of educators and to bring such expertise into the public policy arena rather than left guarded behind the classroom door.

Teacher learning – collaborative, action-oriented, and co-designed - is fundamental to change. It is underpinned by the same learning principles that determine effective student learning - collaborative, inquiry-focused, and addressing authentic professional problems. Pedagogical innovations require deep changes in teachers' practices and roles in which they are co-designers. Innovations in teaching and learning are not so much assimilated as adopted progressively and creatively by teachers who know how to use their own experiences as “anchors” for implementation and innovation[3]. Training models focusing on imparting knowledge and skills are generally not effective in bringing about change in pedagogical practice, as compared with providing experiential, iterative, action-oriented learning with teachers collaborating in well targeted communities of practice. Networks are critical in this process, emphasizing the transformation of culture and practice. They emphasize trust and partnerships with families, employers and the wider community in support of change and in this underline the need for a strong focus on implementation, and maintaining focus

with all on board. Successful change can be understood as a process of learning, with change at one level being promoted by the alignment and mutual reinforcement of the other levels. Scale matters and stakeholders at different levels need to be engaged in a process of learning for the innovation to be scaled. Scalable adaptations have often evolved from the original model inspiration and may well not be high-fidelity replications.

For both policy and practice, it is useful to consider pedagogy in the space that lies between broad principles and specific teaching methods and practices. Pedagogical approaches populate the middle ground on this spectrum. They are more practically oriented than the theoretical models at one end of the spectrum, while yielding insights that are more easily generalised than the discrete practices that lie at the other end of the spectrum. Six broad clusters of pedagogical approaches were developed for this volume through literature searches and consultations with diverse experts. They are: blended learning, gamification, computational thinking, experiential learning, embodied learning, and multiliteracies and discussion-based teaching. These clusters are not stand-alone approaches, since these pedagogies share key features. They are all strongly focused on learner engagement and collaboration; they foster critical thinking and are grounded in what is relevant to learners; and they all can exploit the potential of digital technologies[4]. The clusters can be organized and combined in different ways to enhance their effectiveness and to create unique approaches to teaching and learning. Combining the approaches means moving beyond the fragmented focus on specific pedagogical innovations to highlight the importance of the creative work of teachers and schools when adjusting, adapting, mixing and updating the clusters of innovative pedagogies.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that teachers are the ultimate role models for students. The fact that students come into contact with many different types of teachers in their academic career means that more likely than not, there will be a teacher that speaks to them. The teacher-student

connection is invaluable for some students, who may otherwise not have that stability. Teachers will stay positive for their students even when things can seem grim. A great teacher always has compassion for their students, understanding of their students' personal lives, and appreciation for their academic goals and achievements. Teachers are role models for children to be positive, always try harder, and reach for the stars. Teachers increase productivity and creativity of students and therefore, of future workers. When students are pushed to be creative and productive, they are more likely to be entrepreneurial and make technological advances, ultimately leading to economic development of a country.

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